

Engineering Properties of Soft Clay Stabilized with Sodium Bentonite for Road Subgrade Improvement

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Abstract

Constructing roads on soft clay subgrades is problematic due to low bearing capacity and high compressibility. This study examines sodium bentonite as a potential stabilizing agent to improve the engineering properties of soft clay from Dhaka, Bangladesh. An experimental program was undertaken, where clay and sodium bentonite (0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% by dry weight) were mixed in varying proportions. Subsequently, each combination was subjected to geotechnical engineering tests, focused on Atterberg limits, Standard Proctor compaction, and Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS). The findings demonstrate the extent to which sodium bentonite improves the soil. The UCS value of the natural clay was 33.06 psi, which improved to a value of 62.79 psi (close to 90% improvement in strength) with the addition of 10% sodium bentonite. Strength development was counteracted with the addition of bentonite content at 15%. The results confirm that approximately 10% sodium bentonite stabilizes soft clay extremely well, which is a practical and reasonable improvement for the quality and performance of highway subgrades in areas with problematic soils.

Keywords: *Sodium Bentonite, Soft Clay, Soil Stabilization, Unconfined Compressive Strength, Road Subgrade.*

Introduction

The foundation of road infrastructure's durability and sustainability lies in the quality of the subgrade and the subgrade's materials. Soft, weak clay soils are one of the most challenging soils for road infrastructure, especially in the Bangladesh delta and alluvial plains. Soft clay soils are weak in shear strength, highly compressible, and moisture sensitive. Therefore, roads built on highly compressible clay soils experience rapid settlement, critical rutting, and surface fatigue cracking within the service life of the road, which creates safety issues and increases maintenance costs. Because of the rapid urban development of megacities like Dhaka and the shortage of suitable infrastructure, in-place soils highly increase the challenge to the engineer to come up with effective, rational, and sustainable ways to relieve the pressure on road clay soils.

Soil stabilization systems improve weak soils for sustainable construction. This ground improvement technique alters the properties of the weak and problematic soils of construction sites. The method adds

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materials to the soil to increase construction soil strength, durability, and resistance to deformation. Integrated ground improvement has been executed for decades using traditional cementing materials like lime and cement. The cementing materials change soil properties through cation exchange and pozzolanic reaction, which increases construction soil strength while decreasing plasticity. The production of lime and cement is highly energy-intensive and environmentally damaging. This has shifted interest to the use of cheaper and more eco-friendly options. The last couple of years have seen many researchers try to use a wide variety of materials to replace or complement conventional stabilizers, which include cement and lime. Some of the materials trialled include industrial by-products such as fly ash, natural and synthetic fibres.

Among these alternative materials, bentonite clay, specifically sodium bentonite, has generated a lot of interest due to its exclusive physicochemical characteristics. Sodium bentonite is a natural clay mineral mostly comprised of montmorillonite that has the potential to swell extraordinarily, has a large specific surface area and has a highly developed cation exchange capacity. The soft clay mineral voids and matrix homogeneity created through chemical bonding of soil particles assists in mechanical performance enhancement to the soil. Though there are numerous studies on geotechnical applications of bentonite, its particular potential on executing soil stabilization techniques on the soft clays of the Dhaka area, which is a problematic region for road subgrade, requires more scrutiny.

This research tries to fill this gap by conducting thorough experimental research on the use of sodium bentonite as a stabilizing agent for soft clay collected from Uttara, Dhaka. This study's main goals are as follows: (1) to understand how the various percentages of sodium bentonite added to the soft clay affects the physical and mechanical properties determined quantitatively, (2) to find the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) of the different soil mixes to determine the optimal bentonite content for maximum strength gain, and (3) to evaluate how the stabilizer affects the soil's Atterberg limits. This research is entirely confined to a lab where the soil was prepared with 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% sodium bentonite by dry weight and a standard set of geotechnical tests was conducted. This research is the first of its kind as it focuses specifically on a problematic soil type in one of the major cities, to provide actionable results for the local engineering community. The findings aim to add meaningful information to soil stabilization while providing a practical approach to road subgrade construction in Bangladesh and other places with comparable geotechnical issues.

Current Status

Soil stabilization is a very important part of geotechnical engineering, as it seeks to improve the characteristics of problem soils so they can support civil engineering construction. A huge amount of research focuses on finding different stabilizers and their impact on various soil types. The most common improvements sought for problem soils, especially soft clays, include gaining strength, becoming less compressible and getting control over the swelling, shrinking, and overall expansive behaviour.

Historically, the most common soil stabilization treatment is the use of cement and lime, which are the most common calcium-based binders. Cement also continues to be the best binder for most construction materials. When cement is mixed with clayey soil, it leads to soil plasticity index improvements and soil strength and stiffness improvements because of a series of chemical reactions of soil-cement interaction, including cation exchange, flocculation-agglomeration, and long-term pozzolanic reactions. Unfortunately, cement and lime production, especially cement production, has a huge climate impact with an unsustainable amount of CO₂, a fact which is often overlooked. Most researchers, including Barman and Dash (2022), fully appreciate all the engineering uses and advantages of cement and lime. Still, they also focus on the climate impact and the need for 'greener' geotechnical engineering alternatives.

To address these environmental concerns, many research studies have looked into the potential of using soil stabilizers made of industrial by-products and waste materials. Fly ash, which results from the burning of coal and is a pozzolanic material, has also been studied to a great extent as a potential partial or complete cement substitute. It has been established that fly ash has great potential as a soil stabilizer because it improves CBR and UCS subgrade soil strength, thus providing both an inexpensive and more environmentally friendly soil stabilization practice. Regarding the enhancement of soil properties, the use and incorporation of fibres, either synthetic or natural, notably polypropylene and coir, improves the tensile strength and ductility of clay soils. This soil matrix is particularly useful for dynamic loading because it helps prevent cracking and improves resiliency, providing overall enhancement to the soil.

There are a lot of natural options to be investigated, and bentonite clays have shown to be reliable stabilizers. Bentonite, and more specifically sodium (Na) bentonite, is made mostly of montmorillonite, which is one of the more common clays described in ancient literature and which is one of the main three-layer clays. It has a high cation exchange capacity, which in turn enables it to absorb large quantities of water and swell. When Na-bentonite is a stabilizer for non-expansive clays, it is especially useful as a binder and filler. It helps to improve the texture of the soil by making it denser and more homogeneous, as its extremely fine-grade clay particles blend well with the soil matrix. Also, the surface charge of montmorillonite is of great value, resulting in the formation of numerous strong electrochemical bonds that are cohesive with other clay particles, thus increasing cohesion and shear strength of the mass. Barbieri et al. (2022) studied the effects of both types of bentonite as stabilizers and concluded both were optimal in improving the resilient modulus and reducing permanent deformation, supporting the evidence of bentonite bonding physically to the aggregate particles.

The right amount of bentonite is crucial when it comes to determining the degree of improvement. In small amounts, bentonite will improve the strength value; however, in larger amounts, the strength value will diminish. This is because bentonite absorbs a lot of water, which in turn reduces the dry density of the soil and increases the soil's plasticity. New research has investigated the usage of bentonite in its nano form. Cheraghalikhani et al. (2023) claimed that adding 3% nano-bentonite to a clayey sand soil resulted in an increase of its unconfined compressive strength (UCS) by 2.3 times. That improvement was significantly higher than that achieved using micro-bentonite. This shows that the increased reactivity and surface area of the nanoparticles allow the stabilization process to become more efficient.

Table 1. Summary of Recent Literature on Soil Stabilization

Author(s) & Year	Stabilizer(s) Used	Soil Type	Key Findings
Barbieri et al. (2022)	Sodium & Calcium Bentonite	Road Aggregates	Both bentonites significantly improved resilient modulus and reduced permanent deformation.
Cheraghalikhani et al. (2023)	Micro- & Nano-Bentonite	Clayey Sand	3% nano-bentonite increased UCS by 2.3×; nano-particles were significantly more effective than micro-particles.
Barman & Dash (2022)	Lime, Cement, Fly Ash (Review)	Expansive Soils	Chemical additives effectively reduced swelling and enhanced strength; environmental concerns are driving new research.
Shen et al. (2021)	Fiber Reinforcement	Clay Soils	Fibre inclusion increased shear strength parameters and prevented the development of cracks.
Pokharel et al. (2021)	Calcium Bentonite & Fly Ash	Organic Soil	10% Ca-bentonite + 30% fly ash improved compressibility and undrained shear strength effectively.

Most studies still focus on expansive soils or granular materials, which represent only a part of the broader scope of research. For example, there is little research on the systematic use of sodium bentonite for stabilising specific low-plasticity, soft clay soils of major South Asian deltas, specifically the Bengal Basin, where Dhaka is located. The principles of bentonite stabilization are well understood. However, application rates and expected improvements in performance are relative to the mineralogy and soil characteristics of the parent soil. Hence, the present study aims to provide specific, regionally relevant performance data on sodium bentonite within the context of soft clay subgrades in Dhaka for more sustainable and resilient road construction in the region.

Materials and Methodology

Study Area

Soil samples for this study were taken from Uttara, Sector 7, Azampur Mor, Dhaka, Bangladesh. This specified location is a part of the Madhupur Tract, which consists of alluvial deposits and soft clay formations typical of the Bengal Basin. The studied region has been undergoing rapid urbanization which has made it a representative region for the geotechnical issues associated with road construction projects within Dhaka.

Materials

Soft Clay

This investigation's primary focus was soft clay soil, characteristic of problematic subgrades predominant in Dhaka. This soil was collected as a disturbed sample from a construction site at a depth of approximately 9.14 meters (30 feet). The sample was placed in double hermetically sealed bags to retain the sample's natural moisture, and then transported to the laboratory. The sample required air drying, pulverisation, and then was passed through a No. 40 (425 μm) sieve, where the coarse particles were removed to produce a homogeneous sample.

Sodium Bentonite

For this research, the stabilizing agent was sodium bentonite powder, which is commercially available. Sodium bentonite was selected for its high swelling capacity and the extensive literature surrounding its binding agent characteristics within soil mixtures. The powder was a fine, off-white powder and was used as is, without any alterations, as received from the supplier. In this particular case, the bentonite was meant to strengthen the soil and alter its plastic behaviour through its interaction with the clay particles.

Figure 1. Sodium Bentonite

Sample Preparation and Mix Design

An investigation on the impact of sodium bentonite on soft clay involved the preparation of four distinct mixtures. Sodium bentonite was incorporated in the dry clay at the rates of 0%, 5%, 10%, and 15% of the clay's dry weight. The 0% mixture was considered as the 'control sample' to reflect the natural and unstabilized soil. For every mixture, the dry soil and sodium bentonite powder were proportioned and mixed in a mechanical mixer for several minutes, followed by the addition of water, which was calculated based on the compaction tests, and mixed to the soil to create a homogenized paste. The mixtures prepared in this manner were subjected to a series of geo-technical tests.

Experimental Testing Program

The program of tests comprised several standard geotechnical laboratory tests as stated by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and was designed to determine the natural soil's physical and mechanical properties and the properties of the homogenised, stabilized mixtures.

Table 2. Summary of Laboratory Tests Conducted

Test Name	ASTM Standard	Purpose
Grain Size Analysis	ASTM D422	To determine the particle size distribution of the natural soil.
Atterberg Limits	ASTM D4318	To evaluate the effect of bentonite on the soil's plasticity.
Specific Gravity	ASTM D854	To determine the specific gravity of the soil and bentonite.
Standard Proctor Compaction	ASTM D698	To determine the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD).
Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)	ASTM D2166	To measure the shear strength of the stabilized and unstabilized soil.

Atterberg Limits

Liquid Limit (LL) and the Plastic Limit (PL) of the soil mixtures were established based on the methods provided in ASTM D4318. LL was established via the Casagrande cup methodology and the PL was established by rolling the soil in to a thread of 3.2 mm in diameter and crumbling. The Plasticity Index (PI) which serves as a fundamental measure of the plasticity of soil, was determined by the difference of the LL and the PL ($PI = LL - PL$).

Standard Proctor Compaction

In line with ASTM D698 (Method A), Proctor Compaction tests were designed to calculate the range of Proctor Compaction moisture contents against the Proctor Compacted Soil Dry Density, which was previously calculated. For the Proctor Compaction test, the soil was consolidated in a 101.6 mm (4-inch) diameter cylindrical mould and was consolidated in 3 equal layers. Each layer was given 25 blows with a 2.5 kg (5.5 lb) hammer dropped from a height of 305 mm (12 inches). This was done for several different moisture contents in order to get the Proctor Compaction Curve, which was used to get the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD).

Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)

To assess the strength improvement of the stabilized soil, the primary method used was the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) test which was done according to ASTM D2166. For every mixture, cylindrical specimens were prepared with a diameter of 38 mm and a height of 76 mm. The samples were

compacted using the Standard Proctor tests to their respective OMC and MDD values. The specimens were tested to failure at a constant axial strain rate of 1% per minute. The strength q_u was determined as the highest axial stress that the specimen sustained during the test.

Figure 2. Sample Preparation

The axial stress (σ) and strain (ϵ) were calculated using the following equations:

$$\sigma = P / A' \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon = \Delta L / L_0 \quad (2)$$

$$A' = A_0 / (1 - \epsilon) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- P = axial load
- A' = corrected area of the specimen ($A' = A_0 / (1 - \epsilon)$)
- A_0 = initial area
- ΔL = vertical deformation
- L_0 = initial height of the specimen

Figure 3. Unconfined Compression Test

Results and Discussion

The outcomes of sodium bentonite's addition to soft clay's engineering properties show the results of laboratory work documented in this section, while the discussion deconstructs these results, explains the mechanism involved in these results, and advances potential literature that best relates to the results.

Physical Characteristics of the Natural Soil

Before any stabilization, the soft clay's baseline properties were first determined. For the grain size distribution, the soil was determined to be fine-grained clay because the majority of clay particles were found to pass the No. 200 sieve. The Atterberg limits' tests produced a Liquid Limit of 32.7% and a Plastic Limit of 26.7%. The Plasticity Index was 6.0% and therefore, according to the USCS, the plasticity of the soil is classified as CL, Low Plasticity Clay. The specific gravity of the soil solids was determined to be 2.41. The properties demonstrated that the sample investigated was typical of the soft compressible clays in the Dhaka region, further confirming the sustainability of the sample.

Table 3. Physical Properties of the Natural Soft Clay

Property	Value
Liquid Limit (LL)	32.7%
Plastic Limit (PL)	26.7%
Plasticity Index (PI)	6.0%
Specific Gravity (Gs)	2.41
USCS Classification	CL

Effect of Bentonite on Atterberg Limits

Sodium bentonite addition impacted the soil's plasticity. The Liquid Limit, Plastic Limit, and Plasticity Index all increased with increased bentonite content. The PI increased from 6.0% for the natural soil to 9.0% for the mixture containing 15% bentonite. This is due to the inherent properties of sodium bentonite, which is mostly montmorillonite. Montmorillonite has a very high specific surface area and a high affinity for water. This causes montmorillonite to absorb water in large quantities and exhibit high plasticity.

Table 4. Atterberg Limits of Soil Mixtures with Varying Bentonite Content

Bentonite Content (%)	Liquid Limit (LL) (%)	Plastic Limit (PL) (%)	Plasticity Index (PI) (%)
0	32.7	26.7	6.0
5	35.5	28.5	7.0
10	38.0	30.0	8.0
15	41.0	32.0	9.0

Compaction Characteristics

Standard Proctor compaction test results are shown in Table 5. For the natural soil without compaction aid, the Maximum Dry Density (MDD) was 17.7 kN/m³ at an Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) of 10.5%. The addition of sodium bentonite revealed a clear trend: MDD decreased while OMC increased. At 15% bentonite content, the MDD was reduced to 16.5 kN/m³ and the OMC rose to 12.0%.

This behavior can be attributed to bentonite's high water absorption capacity. As more bentonite is added, the mixture requires additional water beyond the typical amount needed for compaction to achieve

proper particle lubrication, which increases the OMC. At the same time, the absorbed water within the soil matrix does not contribute to the solid mass, resulting in a lower overall dry density of the compacted soil.

Figure 4. Effect of Sodium Bentonite on Atterberg Limits and Plasticity Index

Table 4. Summary of Compaction Test Results

Bentonite Content (%)	Maximum Dry Density (MDD) (kN/m ³)	Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) (%)
0	17.7	10.5
5	17.3	11.0
10	16.9	11.5
15	16.5	12.0

Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)

Figure 5. Effect of Bentonite on Maximum Dry Density and Optimum Moisture Content

Assessing the Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) of a soil provides a basis for evaluating its suitability for subgrade applications. Results indicate strength improvements with the addition of sodium bentonite, but only up to an optimal point. The natural soil had a compressive strength of 33.06 psi. When 5% bentonite was added, the value recorded was 36.26 psi, showing only a small improvement. The most notable increase, however, was observed at 10% bentonite content, where a UCS value of 62.79 psi was achieved—an increase of nearly 90% compared to the unstabilized soil.

The strengthening of the soil can be explained by the physical and chemical interactions facilitated by bentonite. The fine bentonite particles occupy the voids between the larger clay particles, forming a denser and more interlocked soil fabric. In addition, the close contact of bentonite particles promotes clay particle flocculation and subsequent swelling and aggregation, resulting in a more cohesive soil structure.

In contrast to the strength gain, an increase in bentonite concentration to 15% corresponded to a UCS of 17.48 psi, which is lower than that of the natural soil and represents a significant reduction in soil strength. This loss of strength is attributed to bentonite's excessive swelling and water absorption capacity at higher concentrations.

Figure 6. Stress-Strain Behavior of Soil Mixtures with Different Bentonite Contents

The 10% concentration found to be optimal in this study corresponds with the lower range of concentrations reported in the literature for soil stabilization using bentonite. The significant improvement in strength indicates that sodium bentonite is an effective stabilizer for the soft clays of Dhaka, enhancing their capacity to support road traffic loads.

Conclusion

Sodium bentonite was used as a stabilizing agent to assess the improvement of the engineering properties of soft clay subgrade soil located in Dhaka, Bangladesh. After a variety of tests, I was able to determine the following:

When added, sodium bentonite significantly increased the strength of soft clay as indicated by the Unconfined Compressive Strength. The strength recorded before bentonite addition was 33.06 psi, and the strength improved to 62.79 psi with the addition of bentonite, which is close to a 90% increase. An optimal dosage was 10% sodium bentonite by dry weight. At this point in the soil mixture, the maximum strength was recorded. When more bentonite was added, which in this case was 15%, there was a drop in strength. This defines an optimal point for added sodium bentonite—an increase in strength was recorded up to a 10% maximum; however, further addition produced a reduction in strength. This reduction is attributed to the high levels of absorption and swelling properties of the added sodium bentonite.

The physical properties of the soil changed due to the process of stabilization. The soil became more plastic when the bentonite content was higher, evidenced by the increase in Plasticity Index (PI). Similarly, the Maximum Dry Density (MDD) decreased, and the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) increased. This is in alignment with the addition of bentonite, a fine and highly absorptive material. The increased unconfined compressive strength (UCS) of the sample with the optimal 10% mixture demonstrates the value of sodium bentonite in the stabilization of soft clay intended for road subgrades. This increase in strength translates to improved stability of the subgrade, which will support the pavement layers more efficiently, extend the pavement service life and reduce the frequency of maintenance.

Unlike lime and cement, which increase soil adhesion and have a higher carbon footprint, sodium bentonite is a more cost-effective and environmentally friendly option due to its naturally occurring properties. The low percentage of sodium bentonite required for stabilization further enhances its value in promoting the development of sustainable infrastructure.

Table 5. Summary of Improvements at Optimal (10%) Bentonite Content

Property	Natural Soil (0%)	Stabilized Soil (10%)	Improvement (%)
Unconfined Compressive Strength (psi)	33.06	62.79	+89.9%
Maximum Dry Density (kN/m ³)	17.7	16.9	-4.5%
Optimum Moisture Content (%)	10.5	11.5	+9.5%
Plasticity Index (%)	6.0	8.0	+33.3%

The findings of the study demonstrate the effectiveness of sodium bentonite with the potential to improve the engineering properties of problematic soft clays to make road construction more feasible in areas of Dhaka.

Recommendations

While this study contributes important information on stabilizing soft clay with sodium bentonite, additional studies would enhance the practical applicability of the results. Future studies should be concerned with the long-term performance of the stabilized soil within the parameters of soil cyclic loading and varying environmental conditions, especially dry and wet cycles. It would also be important to perform microstructural assessment, for example, SEM and XRD, which will elucidate fabric and mineralogical changes that account for the increase in strength.

Additional research could involve the development of comparative studies aimed at the different classes of locally available soils and different soil stabilizers to determine which stabilizers will be the most cost-effective in the area. Laboratory results should be confirmed, and real performance evaluated through large-scale field trials and in-situ testing under conditioned traffic loading to validate the stabilized

subgrade. To provide vital information to stakeholders in construction, a recommended thorough cost-benefit analysis would compare the economic justification of sodium bentonite stabilization to traditional ground improvement techniques. This will be of great value to sodium bentonite stabilization.

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